

Direct Visualization of Chemically Resolved Multilayered Domains in Mixed-Linker Metal-Organic Frameworks.

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The modular synthesis approach for assembling inorganic nodes and organic multidentate linkers into reticular solids enables rational engineering in porous materials known as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs). Incorporation of two or more linker types in MOF crystals holds great potential for engineering their pores to achieve complex functionalities, by virtue of chemically heterogeneous domains. However, deciphering how these linkers are distributed in the crystal is challenging due to the insufficient spatial resolution of conventional, chemically sensitive techniques that hinders the verification of rational design. Here we leverage the high spatial resolution and chemical specificity of infrared nanoscopy in combination with high-throughput diffraction-limited hyperspectral photoluminescence imaging to determine the composition of individual multivariate UiO-68 MOF crystals, after linker-exchange with optically-active tetrazine units. Our results reveal that the crystals display a 3-layer onion-like structure composed of a core rich in the parent linker, an intermediate multivariate layer with a gradient in linker composition and a proto-MOF external shell. In this outer layer, a fraction of the linkers' binding groups is hydrogen bonded rather than coordinated with metal nodes, suggestive of superficial reconstruction during the linker-exchange. This study advances our analytical capabilities for studying and engineering heterogeneous domains in mixed-linker MOF crystals down to the nanoscale.

1. Introduction

Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs)¹ are a class of reticular solids consisting of inorganic nodes connected by organic linkers *via* strong directional bonds. Careful selection of their constituent building blocks and synthetic conditions can yield solids of ultrahigh porosity with both high thermal and chemical stability. This modular approach together with many achievable crystal topologies, enables rational design of pores sizes and chemical functionalities and has resulted in the creation of more than 100,000 unique MOFs structures.^{2,4} These features make MOFs promising materials for gas separation/storage,⁵ catalysis,⁶ sensing⁷ and drug delivery⁸ among other applications. The rapid development of reticular chemistry^{3,4} has expanded crystals' topologies and has augmented the compositional complexity of MOF structures by incorporating multiple inorganic ions and/or organic linker functionalities, referred to as multivariate MOFs or mixMOFs. Post-synthetic linker exchange is a general method that yields single or mixed-linker frameworks by replacement of linkers of a MOF with analogues of equivalent connectivity but different functionalities.⁹ Judicious choice of synthetic methods and reaction conditions can yield mixMOFs with different structural arrangements that create distinct micro- or nano-environments for tailoring MOF-guest interactions. However, the many variables in the synthesis and the number of possible structural outcomes makes prediction of chemical functions in mixMOFs challenging. Consequently, there is an increasingly growing need¹⁰⁻¹³ for characterizing and controlling the composition and nano-environments of mixMOFs to engineer their properties towards practical applications. Some of us recently studied the effect of linker distribution in the photoactivity of a family of mixed linker mesoporous crystals, based on the prototypical UiO-68 MOF (see Figure 1a) built from H₂TPDC linker [TPDC

= 1,1':4',1''-terphenyl-4,4''-dicarboxylic acid)).¹⁴ Fine control of the post-synthetic, solvent assisted, linker exchange yielded a set of mixed-linker UiO-68 frameworks incorporating the H₂TZDC photoactive linker [TZDC = 4,4-(1,2,4,5-tetrazine-3,6-diyl)dibenzoic acid]) with controllable average composition and spatial arrangements within an individual crystal, i.e., core-shell or homogeneous distribution. For the average fraction of incorporated TZDC photoactive linker, H₂ evolution experiments revealed a boost of the photocatalytic activity for UiO-68 core/UiO-68-TZDC shell samples compared to the homolinker-UiO-68-TZDC, and UiO-68 with homogeneously mixed TPDC and TZDC linkers, which showed comparable activity. Stability tests after catalytic experiments revealed that the performance was controlled by a compromise between the concentration of photoactive linker in the shell and the chemical stability of the crystals which depended on the distribution of the exchanged linker in the crystal bulk.¹⁴

While techniques for quickly assessing the average composition¹⁵⁻¹⁷ and structure of MOF crystals are essential for optimizing suitable synthetic strategies, the complexity of multivariate MOFs requires mapping chemical functionalities within single MOF crystals and with nanoscale resolution.¹⁸ Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy can determine elemental composition with nanoscale resolution,¹⁹ but cannot identify organic linkers or functional groups. Fluorescence microscopy permits rapid visualization of compositional heterogeneity of both organic and inorganic^{10,13,20} components in MOF single crystals with sub-micrometer resolution but has low specificity. For example, confocal fluorescence microscopy was used to assess the spatial distribution of the TPDC and TZDC linkers in mixed-linker UiO-68 MOFs single crystals revealing a TPDC core (500 nm emission) and a TZDC shell (740 nm, emission). Here, high-throughput, sub- μm resolution, hyperspectral photoluminescence imaging is used in combination with photothermal induced resonance (PTIR), a nanoscale infrared (IR) spectroscopy paradigm, to map the composition of multivariate crystals of the UiO-68 family. Our results show that TPDC-TZDC UiO-68 crystals consist of a hierarchical 3-layer onion-like structure. The UiO-68-TPDC core is surrounded by a $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$ thick TPDC-TZDC MOF, which is covered by a thinner external shell ($< 1.6 \mu\text{m}$ wide). We ascribe this layer to an insoluble TZDC proto-MOF with a significant fraction of the TZDC binding groups forming hydrogen-bonds rather than being coordinated with Zr nodes. We interpret this external layer as a superficial degradation or reconstruction of the crystal surface associated to the linker exchange reaction. We believe that this work will foster engineering of MOF crystals with advanced functionalities and complex compositions.

2. Results and Discussion

Since the seminal discovery by Cavka et al.,²¹ the Zr-based UiO-66 isorecticular MOF series has received widespread attention by virtue of their exceptional chemical and physical properties. The UiO series is built from $\text{Zr}_6(\mu_3\text{-O})_4(\mu_3\text{-OH})_4$ octahedral secondary building units (SBUs) linked by twelve linear dicarboxylate linkers resulting in three-dimensional highly porous networks as shown in **Figure 1a**. This family of MOFs is not only robust but also versatile, as it is amenable to modification by incorporation of many kind of linkers^{21,22} and inorganic clusters,²³ even concurrently i.e., with the multivariate approach.²⁴ In this work, single linker UiO-68 frameworks based on 100 % TPDC or TZDC linkers and mixed-linker MOFs with variable proportions of those linkers were prepared according to a previously reported procedure¹⁴ (see supporting information - SI - for more details). As previously reported, fine tuning of exchange temperature, time and concentrations, enable controlling the loading of the exchanged linker and its spatial distributions within the crystals. Samples with 3 % and 10 % TZDC average compositions and heterogeneous linker distributions, referred to as UiO-68-TZDC_{3%} and UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} respectively, were selected for the study. Although kinetic limitations imposed by the molecular diffusion of the incoming linker and by the controlled breakage and formation of coordination bonds can prevent the formation of homogeneous MOF domains, this eventuality is rarely considered (Figure 1b).

Here the composition of such core-shell crystals was studied with PTIR.²⁵⁻²⁷ This technique also known as AFM-IR, circumvents the light diffraction limit by using the probe tip of an atomic force microscope (AFM) to transduce the sample photothermal expansion that results from light absorption. This way, infrared (IR) absorption spectra and maps are measured with a wavelength-independent spatial resolution as high as ≈ 5 nm (tapping mode)²⁸ or ≈ 10 nm (contact mode),²⁹ i.e., much better than the diffraction limit of mid-IR light ($\approx 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$)³⁰ and of thermal diffusion (typically ≈ 100 nm to ≈ 1000 nm).^{31,32} Notably, the PTIR signal is proportional to the local optical absorption coefficient,²⁶ meaning that PTIR spectra exhibit minimal distortions³³ enabling reliable identification of chemical groups,^{18,34} materials,^{35,36} and secondary structures.^{37,38} These characteristics have fostered broad applications in material science,^{18,39,40} biology,^{38,41} geology, medicine,^{42,43} optoelectronics,^{44,45} nano-optics,⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ art conservation^{49,50} and other fields. Recent reviews discuss

Figure 1. a) The UiO-68 structure consists of 12-connected Zr_6 oxo clusters connected by linear ditopic linkers. The orange and blue spheres depict tetrahedral and octahedral cavities in the framework, respectively. b) UiO-68 crystals containing the H_2 TPDC linkers (yellow) are placed in a solution containing H_2 TZDC linkers (pink) to obtain mixed-linker UiO-68 c) Representative PTIR spectra (p-polarization) of TPDC (red and black) and TZDC (blue) linker crystals. The relative intensity of the absorption peaks depends on the relative orientation of the crystals with respect to the polarization direction. In extreme cases, when dipoles of IR active vibrations are aligned nearly perpendicular to the light polarization direction, the intensity of some peaks nearly vanishes (see black TPDC spectrum at 1590, 1541, 1147, 1017 and 1005 cm^{-1}) leading to substantial crystal to crystal spectral variations (comparison of red and black spectra).

PTIR signal transduction,^{26,32} measurement modalities²⁵⁻²⁷ and applications²⁵⁻²⁷ in detail. For example, PTIR was used to map the distributions of two constituent linkers in In-MIL-68 mixMOF single microcrystals as a function of synthesis conditions,¹⁸ and has enabled understanding and speed-up (20-fold) the growth rate of HKUST-1 thin films.⁴⁰ The development of ultrasensitive, wide-bandwidth, nanoscale AFM probes capable of detecting the time-domain sample thermalization⁵¹ in PTIR experiments has also enabled measuring the thermal conductivity of HKUST-1 single microcrystals with nanoscale resolution.⁵²

In this work, a 90° off-axis parabolic mirror directs the light (910 cm⁻¹ to 1850 cm⁻¹) from a quantum cascade laser (QCL) at 20° with respect to the sample surface and focuses it to a ≈ 40 μm spot size. We resonantly excite the AFM cantilever operating in contact mode by matching the repetition rate of the QCL to one of the cantilever's mechanical (contact) resonances^{26,53} (e.g., ≈ 180 kHz) and maintain the frequency match with a phase-locked loop (PLL).⁴³ The resonant excitation amplifies the cantilever oscillation and the PTIR signal by $Q/(2\pi)$ where Q (typically 25 to 250) is the Q -factor of the cantilever resonance used.²⁶ Importantly, for the relatively low excitation frequencies³² used here, PTIR probes the sample composition at depths that reach up to ≈ 1 μm,^{54,55} and not just the top surface of the sample. Compared to our previous work on In-MIL-68 mixMOF microcrystals, the resonant excitation scheme used here improves the signal to noise ratio and the measurement throughput by ≈ 25x and ≈ 625x, respectively.

Representative PTIR spectra (p-polarization) of drop cast TPDC and TZDC linker crystals are shown in **Figure 1c**. Since, the most characteristic peak of the tetrazine moiety (C=N ring stretching) expected between ≈ 1200 cm⁻¹ and ≈ 1250 cm⁻¹)^{56,57} is not prominent, the spectra of the two linkers are quite similar as their spectral intensities are dominated by vibrations from the 1,4-di-substituted benzene rings. Beside a small shift of the hydrogen bonded carboxylic acid peak at ≈ 1684 cm⁻¹, the two linkers show some differences in the C=C stretching spectral region (≈ 1500 cm⁻¹ to ≈ 1600 cm⁻¹) and C-H in plane bending region (≈ 1000 cm⁻¹ to ≈ 1200 cm⁻¹). However, comparison of representative spectra of the two linkers obtained with s- and p-polarization (**Figure S6** and **Figure S7**) show that the anisotropy of the crystals affects the relative intensities of the IR absorption peaks, which are functions of the angle formed by the polarization direction and the principal axis of the crystals. Upon deposition the orientation of the crystals with respect to the light polarization is random, so the relative spectral intensities of the nanoscale PTIR spectra vary from crystal to crystal (see **Figure 1b**). In extreme cases, this effect can almost suppress selected IR absorption peaks when the associated molecular dipole direction is perpendicular to the light polarization direction (see black and red spectra in **Figure 1b**). This is also case for the relatively weak tetrazine C=N ring stretching peak (≈ 1250 cm⁻¹, **Figure S7**, and **Figure S8**). Crystal anisotropy can also cause minor spectral shifts (typically < 2 cm⁻¹) due to the crystal orientation with respect to light polarization direction (**Figure S6** and **S7**).

Since the as synthesized MOF crystals (typically 20 μm to 50 μm wide) were too thick for direct AFM and PTIR characterization, the crystals were dispersed in a hydrophilic acrylic resin. After curing, the resin block containing the MOF crystals was microtomed in nominally ≈ 0.5 μm thick slices which were deposited on a ZnSe substrate for PTIR analysis. Many of the crystal sections obtained in this way were too rough for AFM imaging, but several crystals cleaved with moderate roughness and were amenable to PTIR characterization. We note that sections of UiO-68-TZDC crystals were much rougher and harder to measure than sections of UiO-68-TPDC and of mixed-linker MOFs with TZDC ≤ 10 %. In **Figure 2e** we compare representative PTIR spectra (p-polarization) of UiO-68-TPDC (red), UiO-68-TZDC (blue) and of the polymer matrix (black). The presence of a polymer carboxylic acid peak at 1730 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the two MOF samples suggests that the polymer was smeared above or below the MOF crystals upon slicing. Unluckily, the broad polymer peak with maximum at ≈ 1272 cm⁻¹ spectrally overlaps with the weak tetrazine C=N ring stretching peak at ≈ 1250 cm⁻¹, making direct identification of this chemical moiety in the IR spectra very challenging. Although UiO-68-

Figure 2. a) AFM topography map of a UiO-68-TPDC microtomed crystal within a polymer matrix and corresponding PTIR absorption maps at b) 1595 cm⁻¹ (UiO-68-TPDC MOF) c) 1683 cm⁻¹ (TPDC linker) and d) 1725 cm⁻¹ (polymer matrix). Panels a-d were recorded with a 0.3 Hz scan rate and a pixel size of 9.7 nm and 26.2 nm in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. Scale bars are 500 nm. e) Representative PTIR spectra (p-polarization) of the UiO-68-TPDC sample obtained in the numbered, color-coded locations indicated in panel-2a and compared with UiO-68-TZDC representative PTIR (p-polarization) spectrum).

TPDC is generally characterized by sharper peaks than UiO-68-TZDC, the spectra of the two homolinker MOFs (**Figure 2e**) are very similar, with most spectral features strongly overlapped. Representative PTIR absorption maps of UiO-68-TPDC and UiO-68-TZDC homolinker crystals are shown in **Figure 2** and **Figure S8** respectively. Notably, the linker peaks at 1692 cm⁻¹ (TZDC) and 1684 cm⁻¹ (TPDC) seen in **Figure 1b**, characteristic of hydrogen-bonded carboxylic acids, are absent in the spectra of the two MOFs (**Figure 2e**), indicating that the linkers have been incorporated in the MOF crystals. However, the spectrum in position 4 (green) at the periphery of the UiO-68 crystal strongly resembles the spectrum of the TPDC linker (see black spectrum in **Figure 1b**). The PTIR map at 1684 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded carboxylate in the TPDC linker) shows that in some areas the linker layer adheres to the MOF crystal, and it is also present in areas nearby, which presumably broke off from the crystal surface upon slicing. This finding was unexpected since the MOF crystals were washed extensively after synthesis (i.e., 3 times in *N,N*-Dimethylformamide, 3 times in acetone) and exchanged in hexane before drying. PTIR maps from a different UiO-68-TPDC crystal (**Figure S9**) depict a similar picture and confirms that the TPDC linker residue does not form a complete shell around the MOF crystal. Confocal fluorescence microscopy images from a previous study,¹⁴ showed UiO-68-TPDC crystals with localized clustering of material and not completely smooth surfaces, like the morphology revealed by PTIR maps in **Figure 2** and **S9**.

PTIR maps and spectra obtained on a representative UiO-68-TZDC_{3%} crystal (Figure 3) clearly reveal a core shell structure, with a $\approx 18 \mu\text{m}$ wide core and a shell thickness ranging from $\approx 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ to $\approx 1.7 \mu\text{m}$, depending on the location. PTIR maps with the sharpest compositional contrast were obtained at 1732 cm^{-1} (polymer matrix, Figure 2b), 1412 cm^{-1} (MOF crystal core, Figure 2c) and at 1683 cm^{-1} (shell, Figure 2d). In addition to having distinct IR absorption features, the shell also displays a finer grain texture than the crystal core as revealed by AFM topography (Figure 2a). Supplementary PTIR maps in Figure S10 provide a similar depiction but show slightly reduced contrast due to partial spectral overlap of the different phases at those wavelengths. Beside the spectral contributions afforded by the polymer layer (probably underneath the cross section), the PTIR spectrum of the crystal core (Figure 2f, blue) matches very closely the spectrum of UiO-68-TPDC, as expected. However, the spectrum of the shell (see peaks at 1683 cm^{-1} and 1608 cm^{-1}) is peculiarly distinct from the spectra of the two prototypical homolinker MOFs; i.e., it is not made of UiO-68-TZDC MOF. Subtracting the spectral contribution of the polymer matrix from the spectrum of the shell reveals a spectrum (Figure 3f, green) that show strong similarities to the spectra of the TPDC and TZDC linkers. The prominent peak at 1683 cm^{-1} suggest that shell has substantial amount of the linker binding groups that are hydrogen bonded rather than fully incorporated in the MOF framework. This unexpected layer is insoluble (the MOF crystals were cleaned extensively after synthesis) and it is ascribed to a proto-MOF (see further discussion). Unluckily, the generally strong spectral overlap between the TPDC and TZDC linkers and the polarization dependence of the IR absorption intensity makes quantification of TZDC fraction in the shell or MOF crystal not practical. For example, qualitative distinction between the TPDC and TZDC is in principle possible based on the C-H in plane bending absorptions at $\approx 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, since TPDC has a doublet at 1005 cm^{-1} and 1017 cm^{-1} , while TZDC is characterized by a single peak at 1015 cm^{-1} . However, those peaks are generally weak and their strong intensity

Figure 3. a) AFM topography map of a UiO-68-TZDC_{3%} microtomed crystal within a polymer matrix and corresponding PTIR absorption maps at b) 1732 cm^{-1} (polymer carboxylic absorption) c) 1432 cm^{-1} (core, attributed to UiO-68-TPDC) and d) 1683 cm^{-1} (shell). Panels a-d were recorded with a 0.2 Hz scan rate and a pixel size of 24.5 nm and 78.3 nm in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. Scale bars are $2 \mu\text{m}$. e) Representative PTIR spectra (p-polarization) obtained in the numbered, color-coded locations indicated in panel-3a. f) Comparison of the difference spectrum (green) obtained by subtracting the polymer spectrum to the shell spectrum in panel-3e with the spectrum of the TPDC linker (brown, same as crystal-2 spectrum in Figure 1c), and with the spectrum of the TZDC linker (purple, same a TZDC spectrum in Figure 1c).

dependence on light polarization and crystal orientation (which is uncontrolled in the experiments) make PTIR quantification of local compositions challenging. Similarly, the comparatively weak C=N ring stretching peak at $\approx 1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is spectrally overlapped with the broad polymer peak with maximum at $\approx 1272\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Although the core shell structure revealed by PTIR is conceptually similar to the one inferred with confocal fluorescence microscopy in **Figure S5b** and in a previous work,¹⁴ the shell in **Figure 2d** (1683 cm^{-1} absorption) is thinner ($< 2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) than the shell thickness revealed by TZDC fluorescence in **Figure S5b** ($\approx 3.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ on average). PTIR analysis of the UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} sample (**Figure 4**) similarly reveals crystals consisting of a predominantly UiO-68-TPDC MOF core surrounded by a proto-MOF shell (peaks at 1683 cm^{-1} and 1608 cm^{-1}). This interpretation is confirmed by SEM-EDX (energy dispersive X-ray analysis) which doesn't show difference in the Zr content between the inner and outer part of the crystals (see **Figure S11**). The large crystal in **Figure 4** has a $\approx 34\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ wide core at the widest point and a shell width ranging from $\approx 700\text{ nm}$ to $\approx 1600\text{ nm}$, depending on the location. The smaller crystals (cores between $3\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $7\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) also have shells with width ranging from $\approx 700\text{ nm}$ to $\approx 1750\text{ nm}$. In contrast the shell thickness revealed by TZDC fluorescence (**Figure S5c**) is between $4\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $9\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ ($\approx 6.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ on average).

Figure 4. a) AFM topography map of a UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} microtomed crystals within a polymer matrix and corresponding PTIR absorption maps at b) 1415 cm^{-1} (core, attributed to UiO-68-TPDC) and c) 1688 cm^{-1} (shell). Panels- 4a-c were recorded with a 0.08 Hz scan rate and a pixel size of 39.1 nm and 117.2 nm in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. d,e) High-resolution PTIR absorption maps obtained from the area delimited by the green rectangle in panel-4a at d) 1598 cm^{-1} (cores, attributed to UiO-68-TPDC) and e) 1688 cm^{-1} (shell). Panels- 4d,e were recorded with a 0.1 Hz scan rate and have a pixel size of 20.6 nm and 54.7 nm in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. f) Representative PTIR spectra (p-polarization) obtained in the numbered, color-coded locations indicated in panel-4a. The spectra are displayed in common scale.

To gain better insights of this apparent discordance, we obtained detailed hyperspectral photoluminescence (PL) maps of UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} crystals (**Figure 5**), where the full PL spectrum is obtained in each pixel. TZDC and TPDC molecules luminesce when excited with 532 nm (**Figure 5a**) and 415 nm (**Figure S12**) light, respectively. Upon 415 nm excitation, the PL map at 470 nm (**Figure 5b**) shows that the UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} crystals have a UiO-68-TPDC core surrounded by a layer with decreasing intensity towards the periphery of the crystal.

Figure 5. a) Representative average PL spectra (532 nm excitation) for homolinker UiO-68-TZDC (red) and from TZDC linker (blue). b) PL map (470 nm emission, 415 nm excitation) of UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} within a polymer matrix, highlighting the UiO-68 core. c) PL map (600 nm emission, 532 nm excitation) of UiO-68-TZDC_{10%} showing TZDC in the crystal outer portion. d) $I^{660/580}$ PL intensity ratio map obtained by dividing pixel by pixel the PL intensity at 660 nm with respect to the PL intensity at 580 nm. e) $I^{600/680}$ PL intensity ratio map showing regions where TZDC linker is incorporated within the MOF structure. f) $I^{600/580}$ PL intensity ratio map showing regions where TZDC linker is incorporated in the proto-MOF layer. g) False-color reconstructed PL image highlighting the 3-layer structure: UiO-68-MOF core (I^{470}), blue the TPDC-TZDC mixed UiO-68-MOF ($I^{600/680}$) and green TZDC proto-MOF layer ($I^{600/580}$). h) PL spectra (532 nm excitation) corresponding to the numbered, color-coded locations indicated in panel-5c. The spectra are displayed in common scale. i) PL intensity line cuts along the white line in panel-5g for PL intensity at 470 nm (I^{470} , blue), 600 nm (I^{600} , red), PL intensity ratio $I^{600/680}$ (black) highlighting regions where TZDC molecules are incorporated within the MOF structure and PL intensity ratio $I^{600/580}$ (cyan) highlighting region where TZDC molecule are incorporated into a precursor proto-MOF phase. Scale bars are 10 μm .

Consistently, upon 532 nm excitation, the PL map at 600 nm in Figure 5c shows a dark UiO-68-TPDC core with a $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$ wide TZDC-rich shell which we attribute to mixed TPDC/TZDC UiO-68. Some localized areas show strong 600 nm intensity which we attribute to TZDC linker presumably broken off by the

microtoming procedure. The PL spectra (532 nm excitation) of reference TZDC linker and UiO-68-TZDC MOF crystals (**Figure 5a**) show relatively small, but significant, differences. In particular, the luminescence maximum shifts from ≈ 582 nm for UiO-68-TZDC to ≈ 602 nm for the TZDC linker. The latter also is characterized by a broader emission and shows stronger luminescence at the longer wavelengths, e.g., 680 nm. A pixel-by-pixel $I^{660/580}$ PL ratio map (**Figure 5d**) reveals a 3-layer onion-like structure with a very thin (< 2 μm) bright layer at the periphery which is attributed to a TZDC rich proto-MOF layer where the linker molecules are not fully coordinated into a MOF crystal structure, consistently with PTIR data. The dark intermediate layer is instead attributed to the TPDC-TZDC mixed UiO-68-MOF. Other PL ratio maps $I^{600/680}$ (**Figure 5e**) and $I^{600/580}$ (**Figure 5f**) highlight regions of mixed TPDC/TZDC UiO-68 MOF and TZDC proto-MOF, respectively. The 3-layer onion-like structure of the crystal is better visualized in the false-color reconstructed PL image in **Figure 5g** where red shows the UiO-68-MOF core (PL 470 nm), blue the TPDC-TZDC mixed UiO-68-MOF ($I^{600/680}$) and green TZDC proto-MOF layer ($I^{600/580}$). The PL spectra (532 nm excitation) obtained across those features (**Figure 5h**, from marked locations in **Figure 5c**) confirm this interpretation since the outer layer (spectrum 2, red) is characterized by longer wavelength PL maximum, and higher $I^{660/580}$ value. **Figure 5i** shows representative line cuts across these layers for PL intensity at 470 nm (blue) and 600 nm (red), which show opposing concentration gradients. Additionally, the $I^{600/680}$ (black) and $I^{600/580}$ (cyan) line profiles highlight the extent of TZDC molecules incorporated within the UiO-68 framework and in the proto-MOF layer, respectively. Data on different crystals (**Figure S13**) corroborate this analysis.

3. Conclusion

In this work nanoscale IR nanoscopy and hyperspectral PL microscopy are used in concert to study the composition of individual mixed-linker MOF crystals of the UiO-68 family, revealing an onion like structure consisting of 3 layers. Typically, a core consisting primarily of unmodified UiO-68, is surrounded by a TZDC-TPDC multivariate layer (5 to 10 μm wide) characterized by a concentration of TZDC molecules that decreases towards the crystal interior. Unexpectedly, an outer, insoluble proto-MOF layer (0.7 to 1.6 μm wide) incorporating mainly TZDC linker molecules that are not fully reticulated within the crystalline framework is also observed. We speculate that this unexpected layer may be a telltale of the partial dissolution of the crystal surface due to the dynamic equilibria concomitant to the between the removal of TPCD connectors and the addition of incoming TZDC units to the framework. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first experimental observation suggesting how solvent-assisted linker exchange reactions might be controlled by the superficial reconstruction of MOF crystals. This finding may have significant implications regarding the chemical stability of MOFs, and in applications where accessible metal sites or binding groups are important such as catalysis and separation. Our measurements also highlight some of the challenges and opportunities presented by crystalline materials for quantitative PTIR analysis with light polarization. We believe that the methods developed in this work will not only stimulate the development of multivariate MOF crystals with advanced functionalities and complex compositions but stimulate efforts for understanding the spatial distribution and hierarchical organization of their molecular components at the micro and nano scales.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

All PTIR experiments were obtained in dry nitrogen atmosphere using commercially available gold-coated contact-mode AFM probes with 0.2 N/m nominal spring constant and ≈ 20 nm apex radius. PTIR spectra (1 cm^{-1} spectral resolution) were recorded by sweeping the laser at 50 $\text{cm}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and were normalized with respect to the laser output intensity (background) measured by pyroelectric detector in proximity of the sample. To

improve the signal-to-noise ratio, ten PTIR spectra were averaged in each location and slightly smoothed using a Savitzky-Golay Filter (3rd order, 5 adjacent points). The scan rate for PTIR images was 0.1 to 0.3 Hz.

A microscope equipped with a complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) camera (1024 x 1024 pixels array, 82% peak quantum efficiency, 37000:1 dynamic range) was used to generate wide field hyperspectral PL maps (2 nm spectral resolution) from 450 nm to 850 nm at a rate of 1 nm/s leveraging two high-throughput Bragg grating filters. TZDC and TPDC molecules were excited with a continuous wave 532 nm laser (3W) and with a 415 nm light emitting diode (7W), respectively. A 100x objective (0.9 numerical aperture, 1 mm working distance) that was used for both excitation and light collection in a 180° backscattering geometry. This configuration resulted in a 65 µm x 65 µm field of view and (≈ 63.5 nm pixel resolution) and an estimated spatial resolution of < 1 µm. PL spectra were normalized by the dark background intensity. Spectral profiles were generated by extracting emission intensity at a given wavelength as a function of position by averaging the intensity of 30 parallel pixel lines. Individual pixel spectra (**Figure 5f**, were smoothed considering 9 adjacent spectral points).

Additional experimental details are included in the supporting information file.

5. Statistical analysis

No statistical analysis was conducted.

6. Conflict of Interests

The authors don't have any financial or commercial Conflict of Interest

7. Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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